

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN THE STUDY OF PROBLEMS IN THE CREATION OF COMPOSITIONAL WORKS

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ABSTRACT

In the process of covering this article, attention was paid to the excellent fact that today it is important to create compositional work and further develop it in the development of students' abilities. In fact, we have also briefly touched on the views of all nations and Hellenes, unlike the Masters of Fine Arts of other eras.

Introduction: each type of Fine Art has its own compositional styles. For example, a book decoration (painting) differs from a monumental mural painting composition. Also, the perception of the composition can vary. For example, from sculptural works, the relief can only be seen from the front. On the contrary, monumental monuments should be turned around and watched. The sculptor must take into account the laws of composition when creating a work. In the visual arts, the multi-form (figure)li cartinas and sculptures are also called

Composition. Throne of results: in Architecture — the composition (incarnation) consists in ensuring the unity of the structure, function and ideological artistic aspects of the building (structure and their complexes)and its place in urban planning; the composition determines the interior rooms with the appearance of an entire city or architectural ensemble, a separate building or structure, decor with structure, Color, Project and construction, In literature, composition is the state, interdependence of various parts that serve the artistic formation of a work, an event, a character-images, lyrical digressions, a statement of details, and so on, subject to a certain purpose. The integrity of the composition of the work is its main condition. Excess character, episode, and detail reduce the cost of the work. That is why there should be no shortage or excess in the work of art. the originality of the composition depends on what order the elements of the plot are arranged, whether there are elements outside the plot (lyrical, philosophical-journalistic retreats, additional episodes), the norm and order of such means as landscape, portrait, psychological image, author's description. the method and methods of creating a composition are diverse. From time immemorial, the composition was understood in close connection with the idea of the work. composition is not just a structure of the work, but the purpose of this structure, on the basis of what it ist In music-

- 1) the structure of a piece of music (see: form of Music);
- 2) the product of the composer's creativity, the work of tugal Music;

3) the process of creating works of multi-voice music, the type of artistic creation;

4) historical-theoretical and practical science taught in conservatory and other musical educational institutions.

The principles of creating musical themes, ways to make good use of multi-voice musical instruments in their development, features of a particular genre of music, types and styles, the structure of works and bringing them into a complete form are expressed in such information as the rules of law. In the visual arts-a tool for a clear expression of the idea of an artist (sculptor and other), in which the skill of the creator is vividly manifested. Through composition, the author organizes lines, shapes, colors and images, assimilates spatial breadth and creates an artistic environment. The basis of the composition is externality, form accuracy and their mutual harmony. Creative creator, This led to a narrowing of the means of expression of the composition. "Stagnant" and "closed" composition during the Renaissance, "dynamic" and "open" K in Baroque art. made priority. In the history of art, an equally important role was played by compositions created subject to laws and efforts to create a composition based on free compositional methods. During the Renaissance, the desire for a scientific justification of the composition is observed. Each type of Fine Art has its own compositional styles. Mac,¹ Book decoration (painting) differs from the mahogany mural painting composition. Also, the perception of the composition can vary. From Mac, sculptural works, the relief can only be seen from the front. On the contrary, monumental monuments should be turned around and watched. The sculptor must take into account the laws of composition when creating a work. In the visual arts, the multi-form (figure)li cartinas and sculptures are also called Composition.. In architecture-composition (incarnation) consists in ensuring the unity of the structure, function and ideological artistic aspects of the building (structure and their complexes)and its place in urban planning; the composition determines the interior rooms, decoration, Color, Project and construction with the structure, harmonization with the environment, with the appearance of an entire city or architectural ensemble, a separate building or structure, This requires a lot of skill from the architect. After all, among the events of the Chronicle plot, it is natural to observe the cause-and-effect (which partially causes the event that happened before), the time relationship between the events of the concentric plot(the result comes after the reason). So, when determining the type of plot in a concrete work, it should be taken into account which of these relations has a leading position. Sometimes plot features of both types appear in the work harmoniously, and the same harmony ensured its charm mu

- For example, in the "Scorpion from the altar "the exposition includes a very large place — episodes from the Khan until the arrival of suitors, in the "blood of the memorial "it is given very short and after the knot, and in the "lights of the troop" the exposition is generally omitted².The knot is the event that triggered the beginning of the events of the work, the place where the conflict of the work is laid. Unlike the exposition, the knot is considered ^{3a}

¹ Baymetov, B. B., & Sharipjonov, M. S. O. (2020). Development Of Students' Descriptive Competencies In Pencil Drawing Practice. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2(08), 261-267

² Рўзинов, Б. А., Нуриддинов, Б. Х., & Каримбоев, Х. Қ. Ў. (2021). МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЙ МЕРОС ОБЪЕКЛАРИ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ МИЛЛИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИМИЗГА БЎЛГАН МЕХРИНИ УЙЎТОИШ. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 99-108

³ ⁴ Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). CURRENT ISSUES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FINE ARTS. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(03), 1-3.5. Sadikovna, S. G., Kurbonova, B., Akhmedova, N., & Sulaymanova,

necessary element of the plot, that is, it is ready every time on the plot. Only in some cases, in particular, in some Chronicle plots, as well as in plots based on the dynamics of the "internal movement", it may not seem exaggerated enough. The knot is usually given at the beginning of the work, after the exposition. Sometimes, with the aim of a certain artistic and aesthetic goal, its role is also changed (for example, in the novel "Days Gone By", Athabek was met with a tambourine of Silver — the knot of the work, but this story is told at the end of the first half)

That is, the non-existence of a literal solution becomes a method that serves to increase the power of influence of the work, the creative activity of the reader. For Example, P.Kadyrov's "Erk", O.Yakubov's "Matluba", "The Wing will be a pair", X.Sultanov's stories such as "the coast of Bliss" face the same situation. So it will be more correct to understand the solution not as a solution to the conflict posed in the work, but as the end, result of the development of events in it. From the above, it turned out that the knot, the development of the story and the culmination are the main elements that hold the plot, and they will be present in any plot. And the solution with the exposition is the unconditional elements of the plot, the presence or absence of which in the work is associated with the creative intention, creative individuality of the writer, the path of artistic image and interpretation. In some literature, the prologue and epilogue are also shown as an element of the plot. There are also some works in which information is given (or described) about the life of the heroes before the plot time of the work (previous history — "predistoria") or after (later history — "posleduyutshaya istoria"), which are also listed among the plot elements. But these items are not directly related to the plot, they are more elements related to the composition. For example, a preface in "Days Gone by", a spring plaque in "day and night" — a prologue, a conflict of Athabek in the novel "Days Gone By" with Zainab in the cemetery — an epilogue, information about his further life can be taken as "further history". In literary criticism, there is a variety in the use of the invasions "Sutra" and "fabula": while some literary critics use these two conquests as synonyms, others distinguish. In particular, representatives of the Russian formal school understand the order in which the events described in the work occur in life by "fabula", and by "Sutra" - the order in which they are placed in the work. There are also some works in which information is given (or described) about the life of the heroes before the plot time of the work (previous history — "predistoria") or after (later history — "posleduyutshaya istoria"), which are also listed among the plot elements. But these items are not directly related to the plot, they are more elements related to the composition. For example, a preface in "Days Gone by", a spring plaque in "day and night" — a prologue, a conflict of Athabek in the novel "Days Gone By" with Zainab in the cemetery — an epilogue, information about his further life can be taken as "further history". In literary criticism, there is a variety in the use of the invasions "Sutra" and "fabula": while some literary critics use these two conquests as synonyms, others distinguish. In particular, representatives of the Russian formal school understand the order in which the events described in the work occur

S. (2020). FUNDAMENTALS OF PROFESSIONALISM DEVELOPMENT ON THE EXAMPLE OF PRACTICAL EXERCISES ON FORMING THE SKILLS AND SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS. PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology, 17(6), 8894-8903.

* Amanullaev, A. "SPECIFIC FACTORS OF COMPREHENSIVE STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF THE HISTORY AND CULTURE OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE." ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603 11.02 (2022): 1-4.

Amanullaev A. SPECIFIC FACTORS OF COMPREHENSIVE STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF THE HISTORY AND CULTURE OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE // ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 02. – C. 1-4.

in life by "fabula", and by "Sutra" - the order in which they are placed in the work. The "mysteriousness" in the narration increases another bahya when the reader observes the behavior of Silver, its thoughtfulness-glazing with water from the yu ditch, their babbling at the girls' meeting. Finally, Silver's "is that you?" when he hears the words full of admiration, the reader is sure that his guess in his language has come out correctly, and the moment he is satisfied, the writer also opens the word from that random meeting. We see that simply this method increases the creative activity of the reader, brings him closer to the psyche of the heroes, increases the power of influence on the charm of the work. The method seen in the example of "Days Gone By" is called retrospection, the essence of which is that the writer stops the events of the plot and moves to the past, to the image of events that took place earlier. While the Almighty used this method only in one place of the novel, retrospection occupies a leading position in the plot construction of some works, in which the past is alternately given by the artistic time of the work. For example, M.M. Do stning. First of all, it is necessary to distinguish between the time of occurrence of the events described in the work of art and the time of their narration. If we conditionally take the time of the occurrence of events in the work as "plot time", the time of the narration of the events of the work as "composition time", then it is seen that these two do not always coincide. Because the writer, working on the work (epic works are meant in this place), can use the possibilities of "artistic time" in different ways on the way to the realization of his creative intention. Suppose that in a necessary place he can retreat from the time of the work and describe events that have occurred in the past ("retrospective time"), respectively describe events that coincide at one time in terms of their occurrence ("parallel time" — this is taken in relation to the main plot line). The fact that the events in the plot of the work formed the illusion of continuity in the reader's imagination (therefore, when we talk about the events of the plot, we say "then this will happen", "so much vaq). For Example, S. In the novel "slaves" by Ayni, events that have passed for more than a century, and in "Scorpion from the altar" - for only about six months, are taken to the pen. Nevertheless, these two novels do not differ much from each other in terms of volume (or time of narration) (in proportion to the time described in them). After all, in the "slaves" built on the basis of the Chronicle plot, the time of composition extended at the expense of the length of the time of occurrence of events, while in the "Scorpion from Mehrab" based on the concentric plot, it expanded at the expense of retrospective and parallel times. So, artistic time is a conditional concept, this conditionality arises with the requirement to fit the plot time into the framework of the composition time. Since the plot of a work of art is composed of events, and events are composed of the actions, mutually complex relationships, contradictions of the characters, it is also defined as a system of events that generalize life conflicts. Between the plot and the conflict, a dual connection is observed: on the one hand, the plot, Conflict (lot. conflict) is understood as the mutual struggle of the characters of a work of art, the conflicts of the hero with his environment, as well as the contradictions that pass in his psyche. The bar of conflicts that exist in the real life of a person is reflected in it artistically, both because the work of art reflects reality artistically, and in its

⁵ Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan Dilmurod Saymamutovich Pulatov Candidate of Arts, Namangan State University, Uzbekistan Email: dilmurodpulatov658@gmail.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v5i7.481>

center is the image of a person. From this point of view, three types of artistic conflict are distinguished:

1. Charactersaroconflikt.
2. Conflict of hero and environment.
3. Internal (psychological) conflict.

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